

Direct pattern techniques for cast post and core: A clinical comparison of resin and inlay wax in anterior tooth restoration

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Abstract

Restoration of endodontically treated anterior teeth with significant coronal loss presents both functional and aesthetic challenges. Custom cast post and core restorations remain a reliable option, especially when there is minimal remaining tooth structure. This case report presents two clinical approaches to custom post fabrication using direct techniques: pattern resin and inlay wax. In Case 1, a 22-year-old male with a fractured maxillary central incisor (tooth #11) following trauma was managed using a resin-based direct impression technique. In Case 2, a 30-year-old male with discoloration and structural compromise of tooth #21 was treated using an inlay wax pattern. Both cases involved post space preparation, preservation of a 4 mm apical seal, and fabrication of a custom metal post and core, followed by full-coverage restorations. Pattern resin offered superior handling, dimensional stability, and ease of removal without distortion. In contrast, inlay wax was more technique-sensitive and prone to deformation. While both techniques resulted in clinically acceptable outcomes, these findings reinforce the importance of material selection based on clinical needs and operator proficiency.

Keywords: Custom cast post and core; Inlay wax; Pattern resin; Anterior teeth

1. Introduction

Managing anterior teeth that have undergone endodontic treatment and exhibit substantial coronal structure loss can be particularly challenging, especially when both aesthetics and function must be restored. In such situations, a custom cast post and core is often the treatment of choice, as it provides a precise fit within the root canal and supports long-term stability of the final prosthesis.^{1,2}

The success of this restoration largely depends on the accuracy of the post space impression. Among the commonly used direct techniques, inlay wax and pattern resin are popular materials, each with unique benefits. Inlay wax is favoured for its ease of use and adaptability within the canal, while pattern resin is known for its dimensional accuracy and resistance to distortion or breakage during laboratory procedures.^{3,4}

This case report describes the clinical approach to restoring an endodontically treated anterior tooth using a custom cast post and core fabricated through a direct impression method. It focuses on the selection and application of inlay wax and resin materials, highlighting the reasoning behind their use and how they influence the final treatment result.

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2. Case report 1

A 22-year-old male presented to the Department of Prosthodontics with the primary concern of a fractured front tooth. The patient reported a road traffic accident that occurred two months earlier, followed by root canal treatment on the maxillary right central incisor (tooth #11) completed one month ago.

Clinical examination revealed an Ellis Class III fracture involving tooth #11 and an Ellis Class II fracture on the adjacent maxillary left central incisor (tooth #21). The remaining dentition displayed signs consistent with generalized dental fluorosis, including enamel discoloration (brown staining) and surface pitting. The surrounding soft tissues were healthy, with no signs of inflammation or discomfort.

A periapical radiograph of tooth #11 confirmed a well-obtured canal, with no periapical pathology evident. The root length and apical seal were deemed adequate, making the tooth an ideal candidate for post-and-core restoration.

Following the clinical and radiographic assessment, it was decided to restore tooth #11 with a custom cast post and core fabricated using a direct resin pattern technique, followed by placement of a full-coverage metal ceramic crown. Tooth #21 was planned to be managed with a composite resin build-up.

To prepare for crown placement, the residual coronal structure of tooth #11 was conservatively contoured. A 2 mm circumferential ferrule was preserved to reinforce fracture resistance and enhance the long-term success of the restoration. Additionally, an incisal contra-bevel was included to improve both mechanical retention and resistance form.

The post space was prepared by removing gutta-percha from the canal of tooth #11, ensuring a 4 mm apical seal was maintained. For pattern fabrication, the canal was lubricated with petrolatum jelly. A prefabricated plastic post served as a scaffold and was coated with auto-polymerizing pattern resin, which was inserted into the canal. The resin was incrementally built to record the canal anatomy accurately. After initial intraoral polymerization, the coronal portion was built up extraorally. The completed resin pattern was then carefully removed, evaluated, and adjusted to ensure a precise fit prior to casting. (figure 1&2)

Figure 1 and 2 Post and core with pattern resin

The resin pattern was invested and cast in a base metal alloy. After try-in and necessary adjustments, the cast post and core was cemented using glass ionomer luting cement.

Impressions were made using polyvinyl siloxane impression material (Aquasil soft putty and Aquasil ultra light body, Dentsply). Marginal fit and occlusion of porcelain fused to metal crown was evaluated and cemented using Type 1 GIC (3M ESPE Ketac™). Follow-up evaluation was done after 6 months.

3. Case report 2

A 30-year-old male patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry with a chief complaint of discoloration and structural compromise of the upper left central incisor (tooth 21) following a history of trauma five years prior.

Extraoral findings were within normal limits. Intraoral examination revealed a discolored and structurally weakened tooth 21 with minimal remaining coronal tooth structure. Tooth 21 was non-tender on percussion.

Root canal treatment was completed satisfactorily, with adequate obturation and no signs of periapical pathology. The amount of remaining tooth structure indicated the need for a post and core restoration prior to prosthetic crown placement.

Based on the clinical and radiographic evaluation, it was decided to proceed with the fabrication of a custom cast post and core using an inlay wax pattern impression technique.

Gutta-percha was removed from the canal of tooth 21 using peeso reamers, maintaining at least 4 mm of apical seal. The canal was dried and lightly lubricated using a petroleum-based medium to prevent wax adhesion to canal walls.

A Pinjet post was selected corresponding to the prepared canal size. It was gently inserted into the post space to serve as a core for wax buildup and to maintain canal orientation.

Green inlay wax was softened and applied incrementally over the exposed Pinjet. A direct wax-up of the core was done intraorally, sculpting the pattern to mimic ideal core dimensions. The wax pattern, with the embedded Pinjet, was carefully removed and inspected for fit and adaptation. (Figure 3)

Figure 3 Inlay wax pattern

After casting procedure, the final metal post and core was tried in and verified radiographically for length, fit, and orientation. The post was cemented using glass ionomer luting cement. (figure 4 &5)

Figure 4 and 5 Cemented cast post and core

4. Discussion

When a tooth has undergone root canal treatment and concomitant loss of coronal structure, placement of a post and core is frequently required to retain a definitive crown restoration. It should be emphasized that a post primarily serves to secure and support the core, it does not reinforce the root itself. The post-and-core concept has been extensively studied, and choosing the right material depends on understanding its physical properties, indications, benefits and drawbacks, as well as the amount of remaining tooth structure and aesthetic requirements.^{1,2,3}

Custom-cast metal post-and-core systems offer several key advantages over prefabricated fiber posts. They are tailored to the exact anatomy of the prepared canal and are cast as a unified structure, reducing the likelihood of dislodgement under functional loads.⁵ Clinical data reports survival rates of 89–98.5% over 7 years for cast post-and-core restorations in severely compromised teeth.⁶ Another important advantage is the ability to adjust the post-core angulation to accommodate proclined anterior teeth, enhancing prosthetic alignment.⁵

On the downside, cast post-and-core restorations require additional clinical visits and laboratory work, increasing time and cost. They can also impair the aesthetic outcome in anterior ceramic crowns by reducing translucency.⁵

Alternatively, pre-fabricated post and composite cores offer aesthetic advantage and reduced the number of appointments and cost. But they display volumetric shrinkage which results in stress concentration at the tooth-post interface.⁵

Among the available techniques for creating custom cast posts, the use of resin and inlay wax patterns are well established and widely practiced. This case report highlights a clinical comparison of both methods in fabricating cast posts, with a focus on clinical handling, accuracy, and outcomes.

The inlay wax technique, is operator-sensitive and prone to distortion due to the thermoplastic properties of wax, especially during removal from the root canal or handling before casting. Studies have shown that wax patterns can undergo significant dimensional changes when exposed to slight temperature variations, contributing to misfit during the casting process.^{4,7}

Conversely, the use of pattern resin (e.g., Duralay or GC Pattern Resin) offers a more stable alternative. Pattern resin exhibits low polymerization shrinkage and provides excellent handling characteristics, allowing for more accurate adaptation within the canal and easy manipulation during fabrication. Additionally, resin patterns are more fracture-resistant and can be removed and repositioned with minimal distortion, making them more reliable for multi-unit or long-span restorations.^{4,7} In the present case, the resin impression offered greater ease of use and predictability, especially in ensuring a passive fit of the final post.

In terms of clinical success, both wax and resin patterns have been used successfully for decades, and the literature does not show significant differences in long-term outcomes when proper technique is followed.^{1,6}

5. Conclusion

In summary, while both inlay wax and resin impression techniques are viable for fabricating custom cast posts, resin pattern techniques provide superior dimensional stability, handling, and accuracy, particularly in complex clinical situations. The choice of technique should be based on operator preference, clinical presentation, and the need for precision. Future developments in digital post-and-core fabrication may eventually supplant traditional methods, but for now, both wax and resin remain effective tools in the restorative dentist's armamentarium.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical approval was not sought for this case report because it describes single clinical case each without any intervention outside of routine clinical care or experimental intervention. Furthermore all identifying information was anonymized to protect patient privacy and written informed consent was obtained from the patient.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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